

Intelligent OLSR Routing Protocol Optimisation for VANETs

Jamal Toutouh, José García-Nieto, and Enrique Alba
Dept. de Lenguajes y Ciencias de la Computación, University of Málaga,
ETSI Informática, Campus de Teatinos,
Málaga - 29071, Spain
Email: {jamal, jnieto, eat}@lcc.uma.es

Abstract

Recent advances in wireless technologies gave rise to the emergence of vehicular *ad hoc* networks (VANETs). In such networks, the limited coverage of WiFi and the high mobility of the nodes generate frequent topology changes and network fragmentations. For these reasons, and taking into account that there is no central manager entity, routing packets through the network is a challenging task. Therefore, offering an efficient routing strategy is crucial to deploy VANETs. This work deals with the optimal parameter setting of the OLSR, a well-known mobile *ad hoc* network routing protocol. A series of representative metaheuristic algorithms (PSO, DE, GA, and SA) are studied in this article in order to find optimal configurations of this routing protocol. In addition, a realistic VANET scenario (based in the city of Málaga) has been defined to accurately evaluate the performance of the network under our automatically optimised OLSR parameter settings. In our experiments, heuristically tuned OLSR configurations result in better QoS than the standard (RFC 3626) and than several human expert configurations.

Index Terms

Vehicular *ad hoc* networks (VANET), Optimised Link State Routing Protocol (OLSR), Metaheuristics, Optimisation Algorithms

I. INTRODUCTION

VEHICULAR *ad hoc* networks (VANETs) [1] are self-configuring networks where the nodes are vehicles (equipped with on-board computers), elements of roadside infrastructure, sensors, and pedestrian personal devices. WiFi (IEEE 802.11 based) technologies are used for deploying such kind of networks. At present, the IEEE group is completing the IEEE 802.11p and IEEE 1609 final drafts, known as “Standard Wireless Access in Vehicular Environments” (WAVE), specifically designed for VANETs. This technology presents the opportunity to develop powerful car-safety systems capable of gathering, processing, and distributing information. A driver assistance system could collect accurate and up-to-date data about the surrounding environment, detecting potentially dangerous situations and notifying the driver [2], [3].

In VANETs, the WiFi limitations in coverage and capacity of the channel, the high mobility of the nodes, and the presence of obstacles generate packet loss, frequent topology changes, and network fragmentation. Thus, a great deal of effort is dedicated to offer new MAC access strategies [4], [5] and to design efficient routing protocols [6], [7], [8]. In turn, in such kind of networks, routing is a challenging task, since there is no central entity in charge of finding the routing paths among the nodes. Therefore, an optimal routing strategy, that makes better use of resources, is crucial to deploy efficient VANETs that actually work in volatile networks.

Finding well-suited parameter configurations of existing *ad hoc* software protocols is a way of improving their performance, even making the difference between a network that does work or does not, e.g., the networks with high routing load suffer from congestion and cannot ensure timely and reliable delivery of real time safety messages [9].

In the present work, we aim at defining and solving an off-line optimisation problem in order to efficiently tuning the OLSR [10], a well-known mobile *ad hoc* network routing protocol, before its deployment. This protocol has been chosen since it is a modern proactive protocol used in highly dynamic *ad hoc* networks. At present, OLSR is being employed in VANETs by a number of authors [11], [12], [13], [14], [15]. These ones use the standard configuration of OLSR as specified in the OLSR RFC 3626 [10], nevertheless, new parameter settings have been proposed in [16], [17] in order to improve the protocol performance. In fact, optimally configuring OLSR represents the true challenge in this article due to the great bandwidth required for its management.

An optimisation problem is defined by a *search space* and a *quality* or *fitness function*. The search space restricts the possible configurations of a *solution vector*, which is associated with a numerical cost by the fitness function. Thus, solving an optimisation problem consist in finding the *least-cost* configuration of a solution vector. In spite of the moderate number of configurable parameters that govern OLSR [10], the number of possible combinations of the values that they can take makes this task very hard.

Due to the high complexity that this kind of problems usually shows, the use of automatic intelligent tools is a mandatory requirement when facing them. In this sense, metaheuristic algorithms [18] emerge as efficient stochastic techniques able to solve optimisation problems. Indeed, these algorithms are currently employed in multitude of engineering problems [19], [20], [21], [22], showing a successful performance. Unfortunately, the use of metaheuristics in the optimisation of *ad hoc* networks (and concretely in VANETs) is still limited, and just a few related approaches can be found in the literature.

In Alba et al. [23], a specialized Cellular Multi-Objective Genetic Algorithm (cMOGA) was used for finding an optimal broadcasting strategy in urban mobile *ah hoc* networks (MANETs). In Dorrnsoro et al. (2008) [24], six versions of a GA (panmictic and decentralized) were evaluated and used in the design of *ad hoc* injection networks. A Genetic Algorithm was also employed by Cheng et al. [25] for solving the multicast routing problem in MANETs. Due to its specific design, Shokrani et al. [26] developed new routing protocols for MANETs based

on Ant Colony Optimisation (ACO). Particle Swarm Optimisation (PSO) algorithm has been used to manage the network resources by Huang et al. [27] proposing a new routing protocol based on this algorithm to make scheduling decisions for reducing the packet loss rate in a theoretical VANET scenario. More recently, García-Nieto et al. [28] optimised the VDTP file transfer protocol in realistic VANET scenarios (urban and highway) by using different metaheuristic techniques.

We here evaluate four different techniques: Particle Swarm Optimisation (PSO) [29], Differential Evolution (DE) [30], Genetic Algorithm (GA) [31], and Simulated Annealing (SA) [32]. We have chosen these algorithms because they represent a wide and varied set of solvers for real parameter optimisation, based in different search/optimisation schemes and strategies. The popular network simulator *ns-2* [33] is used in the evaluation of the *solutions* (tentative OLSR parameters) generated by the optimisation algorithms, and providing the fitness values to guide the search process. A VANET instance has been defined for the simulations by using real data (roads specification and mobility models) concerning a urban area of the city of Málaga, in Spain.

The main contributions of this work are:

- 1) Proposing an optimisation strategy in which a number of metaheuristic algorithms are (separately) coupled with a network simulator (*ns-2*) to find *quasi-optimal* solutions.
- 2) Obtaining OLSR configurations automatically that outperform the standard one and those used by human experts in the current state of the art.
- 3) Generating a realistic VANET scenario based in real area of Málaga (Spain). This instance is available online for the sake of future experiments.

The remaining of this paper is organized as follows. In the next section, the OLSR routing protocol is introduced. Section III gives details of the algorithms used to optimise the OLSR routing protocol. Section IV describes the optimisation design followed to tackle the problem. Section V presents the experiments carried out in this study. Results, comparisons, and analyses are shown in Section VI. Finally, conclusions and future work are drawn in Section VII.

II. PROBLEM OVERVIEW

Exchanging up-to-date information among vehicles is the most salient feature of a VANET. In order to do so, the packets have to travel through the network from one node to the others, what is a complex task in networks having high mobility and no central authority. The routing protocol operates in the core of VANETs, finding updated paths among the mobile nodes in order to allow the effective exchange of information packets. For this reason this article deals with the optimisation of a routing protocol, specifically the Optimised Link State Routing (OLRS) protocol [10]. The performance of this protocol depends significantly on the selection of its parameters [17]. Thus,

computing an optimal configuration for the parameters of this protocol is crucial before deploying any VANET, since it could decisively improve the QoS, with a high implication on enlarging the network data rates and reducing the network load.

A. Optimised Link State Routing Protocol

OLSR is a *proactive link-State* routing protocol designed for mobile *ad hoc* networks (MANETs and VANETs) which show low bandwidth and high mobility. OLSR is a type of classical link-state routing protocol, which relies in employing an efficient periodic flooding of control information using special nodes that act as *multipoint relays* (MPRs). The use of MPRs reduces the number of required transmissions [34].

OLSR daemons periodically exchange different messages in order to maintain the topology information of the entire network in the presence of mobility and failures. The core functionality is performed mainly by using three different types of messages: HELLO, TC (topology control), and MID (multiple interface declaration) messages.

- HELLO messages are exchanged between neighbors nodes ($1 - hop$ distance). They are employed to accommodate for link sensing, neighborhood detection, and MPR selection signalling. These messages are generated periodically, containing information about the neighbor nodes and about the links between their network interfaces.
- TC messages are generated periodically by MPRs to indicate which other nodes have selected it as their MPR. This information is stored in the *topology information base* of each network node which is used for routing table calculations. Such messages are forwarded to the other nodes through the entire network. Since TC messages are broadcasted periodically a sequence number is used to distinguish between recent and old ones.
- MID messages are sent by the nodes to report information about their network interfaces employed to participate in the network. Such information is needed since the nodes may have multiple interfaces with distinct addresses participating in the communications. These messages contain the list of interface addresses which are associated to a node main address.

The OLSR mechanisms are regulated by a set of parameters predefined in the OLSR RFC 3626 [10] (see Table I). These parameters have been tuned without using any automatic tool in [16], [17] and they are: the timeouts before resending HELLO, MID, and TC messages (*HELLO_INTERVAL*, *REFRESH_INTERVAL*, and *TC_INTERVAL*, respectively); the “validity time” of the information received via these three message types, which are: *NEIGHB_HOLD_TIME* (HELLO), *MID_HOLD_TIME* (MID), and *TOP_HOLD_TIME* (TC); the *WILLINGNESS* of a node to act as a MPR (to carry and forward traffic to other nodes); and *DUP_HOLD_TIME*, that represents the time during which the MPRs record information about the forwarded packets.

TABLE I
MAIN OLSR PARAMETERS AND RFC 3626 SPECIFIED VALUES.

Parameter	Standard Configuration	Range
HELLO_INTERVAL	2.0 s	$\mathbb{R} \in [1.0, 30.0]$
REFRESH_INTERVAL	2.0 s	$\mathbb{R} \in [1.0, 30.0]$
TC_INTERVAL	5.0 s	$\mathbb{R} \in [1.0, 30.0]$
WILLINGNESS	3	$\mathbb{Z} \in [0, 7]$
NEIGHB_HOLD_TIME	$3 \times \text{HELLO_INTERVAL}$	$\mathbb{R} \in [3.0, 100.0]$
TOP_HOLD_TIME	$3 \times \text{TC_INTERVAL}$	$\mathbb{R} \in [3.0, 100.0]$
MID_HOLD_TIME	$3 \times \text{TC_INTERVAL}$	$\mathbb{R} \in [3.0, 100.0]$
DUP_HOLD_TIME	30.0 s	$\mathbb{R} \in [3.0, 100.0]$

B. OLSR Parameter Tuning

The standard configuration of OLSR offers a moderate QoS when is used in VANETs [14], [15]. Hence, taking into account the impact of the parameters configuration in the whole network performance, we tackled here the problem of the optimal OLSR parameter tuning in order to discover the best protocol configuration previously to the deployment of the VANET. The standard OLSR parameters are defined without clear values for their ranges. Table I shows the standard OLSR parameter values as specified in the OLSR RFC 3626 [10]. The range of values each parameter can take has been defined here by following OLSR restrictions with the aim of avoiding pointless configurations.

According to that, we can use the OLSR parameters to define a *solution vector* of real variables, each one representing a given OLSR parameter. This way, the solution vector can be fine-tuned automatically by an optimisation technique, with the aim of obtaining efficient OLSR parameters configurations for VANETs hopefully outperforming the standard one defined in the RFC 3626 [10]. Additionally, analytic comparisons of different OLSR configurations and their performances as the ones done in this article can help the experts to identify the main source of communication problems and assist them in the design of new routing protocols.

In order to evaluate the *quality* or *fitness* of the different OLSR configurations (tentative solutions), we have employed the *communication cost* in terms of three of the most commonly used QoS metrics in this area [35]:

- *Packet delivery ratio (PDR)*. Fraction of the data packets originated by an application that a routing protocol delivers. A data packet is counted as delivered when it is received complete and correct by the destination node.
- *Normalized routing load (NRL)*. Ratio of administrative routing packet transmissions to data packets delivered. When counting transmissions, each hop is counted separately.
- *Average End-to-End delay of a data packet (E2ED)*. Average difference between the time the first data packet is originated by an application and the time this packet is received at its destination.

III. THE ALGORITHMS

Before the description of our optimisation strategy, we briefly discuss in this section the metaheuristic algorithms used: Particle Swarm Optimisation (PSO), Differential Evolution (DE), Genetic Algorithm (GA), and Simulated Annealing (SA). These techniques are selected with the aim of experimenting with different population structures, as well as different reproduction mechanisms. We have stated the same stop condition (reaching a certain number of fitness evaluations) in all algorithms in order to simplify the following descriptions.

A. Particle Swarm Optimisation (PSO)

Particle Swarm Optimisation [29] is a population based metaheuristic inspired in the social behavior of birds within a flock, and initially designed for continuous optimisation problems. In PSO, each potential solution to the problem is called *particle* and the population of particles is called a *swarm*. In this algorithm, each particle position p^i is updated each generation g by means of the Equation 1:

$$p_{g+1}^i \leftarrow p_g^i + v_{g+1}^i, \quad (1)$$

where the term v_{g+1}^i is the velocity of the particle, given by the expression

$$v_{g+1}^i \leftarrow w \cdot v_g^i + \varphi_1 \cdot U^+ \cdot (bp_g^i - p_g^i) + \varphi_2 \cdot U^+ \cdot (b_g - p_g^i) \quad (2)$$

In Equation 2, bp_g^i is the best solution that the particle i has stored so far, b_g is the best particle (also known as the *leader*) that the entire swarm has ever created, and w is the inertia weight of the particle which controls the trade-off between exploitation and exploration. Finally, φ_1 and φ_2 are specific parameters which control the relative effect of the personal and global best particles (typically, $\varphi_1 = \varphi_2 = 2$). U^+ is a uniform random value sampled area in (0,1).

Algorithm 1 Pseudocode of PSO

```

1: initializeSwarm()
2: locateLeader( $b$ )
3: while !stopCondition() or  $g < maxGenerations$  do
4:   for each particle  $x_g^i$  do
5:     updateVelocity( $v_g^i$ ) // Equation 2
6:     updatePosition( $p_g^i$ ) // Equation 1
7:     evaluate( $p_g^i$ )
8:     update( $bp_g^i$ )
9:   end for
10:  updateLeader( $b_g$ )
11: end while

```

Algorithm 1 describes the pseudo-code of PSO. The algorithm starts by initializing the swarm (Line 1), which includes both the positions and velocities of the particles. The corresponding bp^i of each particle is randomly

initialized, as well as the leader b (Line 2). Then, during a maximum number of iterations and while the stop condition is not reached, each particle *flies* through the search space updating its velocity and position (Lines 5 and 6), it is then evaluated (Line 7), and its bp^i is also calculated (Line 8). At the end of each iteration, the leader b is updated.

B. Differential Evolution (DE)

Differential Evolution [30] is a stochastic population based algorithm designed to solve optimisation problems in continuous domains. The population consists of a set of individuals (vectors) which evolve simultaneously through the search space of the problem. The task of generating new individuals is performed by differential operators such as the differential mutation and crossover. A *mutant individual* w_{g+1}^i is generated by the following equation (3):

$$w_{g+1}^i \leftarrow v_g^{r1} + \mu \cdot (v_g^{r2} - v_g^{r3}) \quad (3)$$

where $r1, r2, r3 \in \{1, 2, \dots, i-1, i+1, \dots, N\}$ are random integers mutually different, and also different from the index i . The mutation constant $\mu > 0$ stands for the amplification of the difference between the individuals v_g^{r2} and v_g^{r3} , and it avoids the stagnation of the search process.

In order to increase even more the diversity in the population, each mutated individual undergoes a crossover operation with the *target individual* v_g^i , by means of which a *trial individual* u_{g+1}^i is generated. A randomly chosen vector component is taken from the mutant individual to prevent that the trial individual replicates the target individual.

$$u_{g+1}^i(j) \leftarrow \begin{cases} w_{g+1}^i(j) & \text{if } r(j) \leq C \text{ or } j = j_r, \\ v_g^i(j) & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases} \quad (4)$$

As shown in Equation 4, for each component j of the trial individual u_{g+1}^i , the crossover operator chooses both, a random integer value j_r and a random real number $r(j) \in (0, 1)$, uniformly distributed. Then, the crossover probability C and $r(j)$ are compared just like j and j_r . If r is less than or equal than C or j is equal to j_r , then we select the j^{th} element of the mutant individual to be allocated in the j^{th} element of the trial individual u_{g+1}^i . Otherwise, the j^{th} element of the target individual v_g^i becomes the j^{th} element of the trial individual. Finally, a selection operator decides the acceptance of the trial individual for the next generation if and only if it yields a reduction (assuming minimization) in the value of the evaluation function (also called *fitness* function f), as shown by the following Equation (5):

$$v_{g+1}^i \leftarrow \begin{cases} u_{g+1}^i & \text{if } f(u_{g+1}^i) \leq f(v_g^i), \\ v_g^i(j) & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases} \quad (5)$$

Algorithm 2 shows the pseudocode of DE. After initializing the population, the individuals evolve during a number of generations (maxGenerations) and while stop condition is not reached. Each individual is then mutated (Line 5) and recombined (Line 6). The new individual is selected (or not) following the operation of Equation 5 (Lines 7 and 8).

Algorithm 2 Pseudocode of DE

```

1: initializePopulation()
2: while !stopCondition() or  $g < \text{maxGenerations}$  do
3:   for each individual  $v_g^i$  do
4:     choose mutually different( $r_1, r_2, r_3$ )
5:      $w_{g+1}^i \leftarrow \text{mutation}(v_g^{r_1}, v_g^{r_2}, v_g^{r_3}, \mu)$  // Equation 3
6:      $u_{g+1}^i \leftarrow \text{crossover}(v_g^i, w_{g+1}^i, C)$  // Equation 4
7:     evaluate( $u_{g+1}^i$ )
8:      $v_{g+1}^i \leftarrow \text{selection}(v_g^i, u_{g+1}^i)$  // Equation 5
9:   end for
10: end while

```

C. Genetic Algorithm (GA)

Genetic Algorithm [31] is the most popular metaheuristic. GA iterates a process in which a set of parents (generally two) are selected from the whole population with a given selection criterion, they are then recombined, the obtained offsprings are mutated, and finally they are evaluated and inserted back into the population following a given criterion. The mutation process is carried out by randomly (uniformly) selecting one of the elements in the solution, and assigning (randomly) a new value in a specific range. In this work, we use a polynomial crossover defined for continuous variables [31] as the recombination operator. Algorithm 3 summarizes the operations of a canonical GA.

Algorithm 3 Pseudocode of GA

```

1:  $g \leftarrow 0$ 
2:  $P_g \leftarrow \text{initializePopulation}()$ 
3: while !stopCondition() or  $g < \text{maxGenerations}$  do
4:    $P'_g \leftarrow \text{recombine}(P_g)$  // Generate offspring from parents
5:    $P''_g \leftarrow \text{mutate}(P'_g)$  // Offspring mutation
6:   evaluate( $P''_g$ )
7:    $P_{g+1} \leftarrow \text{select}(P''_g \cup P'_g)$  // New population generation
8: end while

```

There are two main versions of GA: *steady State* GA (ssGA) and *generational* GA (genGA). The difference between the ssGA and the genGA is the way in which the population is updated with the new individuals generated during the evolution. In the first one, new individuals are directly inserted into the current population. In the case of the genGA, a new auxiliary population is built with the obtained offsprings and then, once this auxiliary population

is full, it completely replaces the current population. Thus, in ssGAs the population is asynchronously being updated with the newly generated individuals, while in the case of genGAs all the new individuals are updated at the same time, in a synchronous way.

D. Simulated Annealing (SA)

SA was first presented as an optimisation technique in Kirkpatrick et al. [32]. It is inspired in the industrial processes of annealing, and basically lies in a local search method with a mechanism that eventually promotes solutions of worse quality than the current ones (uphill moves) in order to escape from local minima. The probability of performing such a movement decreases during the search process. The pseudocode of the canonical SA is shown in Algorithm 4.

Algorithm 4 Pseudocode of SA

```

1: initialize( $T, S_a$ )
2: evaluate( $S_a$ )
3: while !stopCondition() or  $g < maxGenerations$  do
4:   while not coolingCondition( $g$ ) do
5:      $S_g \leftarrow$  chooseNeighbor( $S_a$ ) // Generate new solution
6:     evaluate( $S_g$ )
7:     if accept( $S_a, S_g, T$ ) then // Acceptance criterion
8:        $S_a \leftarrow S_g$ 
9:     end if
10:  end while
11:  coolDown( $T$ ) // E.g.  $T = T \times 0.999$ 
12: end while

```

The algorithm works iteratively keeping a single tentative solution S_a at any time. In every iteration, a new solution S_g is generated from the previous one, S_a (Line 5), and either replaces it or not depending on an acceptance criterion (Lines 7-8). The acceptance criterion works as follows: both the old (S_a) and the new (S_g) solutions have an associated quality value, determined by a fitness function ($f()$). If the new solution (S_g) does not improve the old solution (S_a), S_g replaces S_a with probability $prob$ (Equation 6). This probability depends on the difference between their quality values and the control parameter T named *temperature*.

$$prob = \frac{2}{1 + e^{\frac{f(S_a) - f(S_g)}{T}}} \quad (6)$$

As iterations go on, the value of the temperature (T) is reduced following a cooling schedule (Line 11), thus biasing SA towards accepting only better solutions [36]. In this work, we employ the geometric rule $T(n+1) = \alpha \cdot T(n)$, where $0 < \alpha < 1$, and the cooling is performed every k iterations (k is the *Markov chain length*).

IV. OPTIMISATION FRAMEWORK

As previously commented, the optimisation strategy used to obtain efficient OLSR parameter configurations is carried out by coupling two different stages: an optimisation stage and a simulation procedure. The optimisation block is carried out by a metaheuristic method, in this case one of mentioned: Particle Swarm Optimisation (PSO), Differential Evolution (DE), Genetic Algorithm (GA), and Simulated Annealing (SA). These four methods were conceived to find optimal (or quasi-optimal) solutions in continuous search spaces, which is the case in this work. Since we need to consider many different scenarios, we use a simulation procedure for assigning a quantitative quality value (*fitness*), in terms of communication cost, to the OLSR performance of computed configurations (tentative solutions). This procedure is carried out by means of the *ns-2* [33] network simulator widely used to simulate VANETs accurately [37]. For this work, *ns-2* has been modified in order to interact automatically with the optimisation procedure with the aim of accepting new routing parameters, opening the way for similar future research.

Fig. 1. Optimisation framework for the automatic OLSR configuration in VANETs. The algorithms invoke the *ns-2* simulator for each solution evaluation.

As Fig. 1 illustrates, when the used metaheuristic requires the evaluation of a solution, it invokes the simulation procedure of the tentative OLSR configuration over the defined VANET scenario. Then, *ns-2* is started and evaluates the VANET under the circumstances defined by the OLSR routing parameters generated by the optimisation algorithm. After the simulation, *ns-2* returns global trace information about the *Packet Delivery Ratio* (PDR), the *Normalized Routing Load* (NRL), and the *Average End-to-End Delay* (E2ED) of the whole mobile vehicular network scenario where there were 10 independent data transfers among the vehicles. This information is used in turn to compute the *communication cost* (*comm_cost*) function as follows:

$$comm_cost = w_2 \cdot NRL + w_3 \cdot E2ED - w_1 \cdot PDR \quad (7)$$

The communication cost function represents the fitness function of the optimisation problem addressed in this paper. In order to improve the QoS, the objective here consists in maximizing PDR, and minimizing both, NRL and E2ED. As expressed in Equation 7, we used an *aggregative minimizing function*, and for this reason PDR was formulated with a negative sign. In this equation, factors w_1 , w_2 , and w_3 (0.5, 0.2, and 0.3, respectively) were used for weighing the influence of each metric on the resultant fitness value. This way, PDR takes priority over NRL and E2ED since we first look for the routing effectiveness and second (but also important) for the communication efficiency.

V. EXPERIMENTS

The simulation task should offer a network environment as close as possible to the real world one. Following this idea, we make an effort to define realistic scenarios where VANETs may be deployed. In this section, we define the urban scenario used in our simulations. Next, we present the experimental set up taking into account the parameter settings for both, the metaheuristic algorithms and the *ns-2* simulation.

A. Urban VANET Scenario

Since *ns-2* is a network simulator of general purpose, it does not offer a way for directly defining realistic VANETs simulations where the nodes of the network follow the behavior of vehicles in a road with other vehicles, traffic lights, traffic signs, etc. In order to solve this problem, we have used a road traffic simulator to generate a realistic mobility model [38]. This tool returns traces with the mobility definitions of nodes that can be used by *ns-2*. The main advantage of employing traffic simulators is that they can be used to generate realistic VANET environments by automatically selecting real areas from freely available digital maps, taking into account road directions, traffic signals, traffic rules, etc. For this task, we have employed SUMO [39], a widely used traffic simulator. The VANET instance defined in this work contains 30 vehicles moving through the roads selected of an area of $1,200 \times 1,200 \text{ m}^2$ from the city downtown of Málaga (Spain) during three minutes. The area inside the dotted line box of Fig. 2 shows the roads taken into account to define the VANET urban scenario for our experiments. Through the simulation time, a set of cars exchange data and, as in a urban road, their speed fluctuate between 10 km/h (2.78 m/s) and 50 km/h (13.88 m/s).

For this VANET scenario, we have defined a specific data flow trustworthy representing different possible communications that may exist. The data flow model performs 10 sessions of a constant bit rate data generator (CBR) which operates over UDP (User Datagram Protocol) agents defined in the nodes (vehicles). This way, the interconnected vehicles exchange the data generated by the CBR agents. The CBR data packet size is 512 bytes and the packet rate is 4 packets per second. The remaining of simulation parameters are summarized in Table II for future reproduction purposes. We have chosen a fixed data rate since we do not aim to study the maximum

Fig. 2. Málaga real urban VANET scenario. Selected area in the city downtown.

throughput, but we want to investigate the ability of OLSR to successfully find and maintain routes in VANET scenarios.

TABLE II
MAIN PARAMETERS DEFINED FOR THE *ns-2* SIMULATION.

Parameter	Value
Simulation time	180 s
Simulation area	$1,200 \times 1,200 \text{ m}^2$
Number of vehicles	30
Vehicle speed	10-50 <i>km/h</i>
Propagation model	Two Ray Ground
Radio frequency	2.47 GHz
Channel bandwidth	5 Mbps
PHY/MAC protocols	IEEE 802.11b
Routing protocol	OLSR
Transport protocol	UDP
CBR data flow	10 sessions

B. Experimental Setting

The experiments have been carried out by using four metaheuristics (PSO, DE, GA, and SA). The implementation of these algorithms is provided by MALLBA [40], a C++ based framework of metaheuristics for solving optimisation problems. Additionally, we have employed a random search algorithm (RAND) also developed in C++. In order to compare these five methods in the OLSR parameter tuning, they have been executed to reach the same stop condition: 1,000 fitness function evaluations. SA and RAND performed 1,000 iteration steps, and population based algorithms performed 100 generations with populations of 10 individuals ($100 \times 10 = 1,000$) each one of them. The main parameters of these algorithms are summarized in Table III. The simulation phase is carried out by running *ns-2* simulator version *ns-2.34*, using the *UM-OLSR (version 0.8.8)* [41] implementation of OLSR. We have performed 30 independent runs of every optimisation technique on machines with Pentium IV 2.4 GHz core, 1 GB of RAM, and O.S. Linux Fedora core 6.

TABLE III
PARAMETERIZATION OF THE OPTIMISATION ALGORITHMS.

Algorithm	Parameter	Symbol	Value
PSO	Local Coefficient	φ_1	2
	Social Coefficient	φ_2	2
	Inertia Weigh	w	0.50
DE	Crossover Probability	Cr	0.90
	Mutation Factor	μ	0.10
GA	Crossover Probability	P_{cros}	0.80
	Mutation Probability	P_{mut}	0.01
SA	Temperature Decay	T	0.80

VI. RESULTS

This section presents the experimental results from three different points of view: first, we show metaheuristic and random search algorithm performances when solving the OLSR optimisation problem. Second, we compare the obtained OLSR parameter configurations against several ones found in the literature. Third, we analyze the influence of the different OLSR parameters in the global QoS provided by the network.

A. Performance Analysis

Table IV shows the mean and standard deviation of the communication cost values obtained (out of 30 independent executions) running all the evaluated metaheuristics and the random search algorithm for the VANET scenario instance. The best, median, and worst values are also provided.

TABLE IV
RESULTS OBTAINED BY METAHEURISTIC AND RANDOM SEARCH ALGORITHMS IN THE OPTIMISATION OF OLSR FOR OUR VANET SCENARIO. RESULTS OF THE STATISTICAL TESTS OF FRIEDMAN AND KRUSKAL-WALLIS (KW) ARE ALSO PROVIDED.

Algorithm	$Mean_{std}$	$Best$	$Median$	$Worst$	$Friedman$	$KW(p\text{-value})$
SA	-0.450297 ±0.024	-0.478242	-0.457451	-0.406932	1.40	3.0591E-6
DE	-0.436897±0.030	-0.480030	-0.435264	-0.392578	2.10	3.0660E-6
PSO	-0.432240±0.033	-0.482343	-0.419734	-0.392503	2.50	3.0669E-6
GA	-0.350837± 0.023	-0.437241	-0.344612	-0.327281	4.33	3.1592E-6
RAND	-0.329878±0.050	-0.410131	-0.329792	-0.217024	4.50	3.3579E-6

We can clearly observe in this table that SA outperformed all other algorithms in terms of mean (-0.450297), median (-0.457451), and worst (-0.406932) communication cost values. According to these measures, SA is followed by DE, PSO, and GA, respectively. Finally, as expected, the random search algorithm obtains worse results than all the metaheuristic algorithms.

In terms of the best OLSR configuration returned by the algorithms (third column), PSO computed the solution with the lowest communication cost (see Fig. 3). The best OLSR parameter settings obtained by DE, SA, and GA are the second, third, and fourth, respectively. RAND best OLSR configuration is the least competitive one.

With the aim of providing these comparisons with statistical confidence we have applied the Friedman and the Kruskal-Wallis tests [42] to the distributions of the results. We have used these non-parametric tests since the resulting distributions violated the conditions of equality of variances (heteroskedasticity) several times. The confidence level was set to 95% ($p\text{-value}=0.05$), which allows us to ensure that all these distributions are statistically different if they result in $p\text{-value}<0.05$.

In effect, confirming the previous observations, the results of Friedman (see sixth column of Table IV) test ranked SA as the metaheuristic algorithm with the best global performance followed by DE, PSO, and GA, respectively. The random search (RAND) showed the worst rank among the compared techniques. Moreover, the multicompare test of *Kruskal-Wallis* applied to the median values of the distributions resulted in $p\text{-values} \ll 0.05$ (last column of Table IV). Therefore, we can claim that all the compared algorithms obtained statistically different results.

Fig. 3. Metaheuristic and random search algorithm best communication cost evolution solving the OLSR configuration problem.

According to the behavior of the optimisation algorithms, we now study the evolution of the best solution (communication cost value) during the whole evolutionary process. Fig. 3 plots the graph of the best communication cost (fitness value) tracked through out the best execution for each algorithm. We can observe that DE, PSO, and SA converge in the same range of solutions. However their evolution is different. The major improvement of the DE solution occurs during the first steps of the execution, unlike what happens with PSO that improves its solution during the last steps. SA, that is the best ranked algorithm according to the Friedman test, performs several gradual improvements of its solution during the whole execution.

Finally, concerning the mean run time that each algorithm spent in the experiments, Table V shows the mean time in which the best solution was found T_{best} (second column), and the global mean run time T_{run} (third column).

GA shows the shortest time ($2.04E+04$ s) to find its best solutions and it seems that this algorithm quickly falls in local optima, hence obtaining weak results (see Table IV). PSO needed the second shortest time ($3.05E+04$ s) to compute its optima followed by DE and RAND, respectively. Finally, SA takes the longest time ($5.78E+04$ s) to find its best solutions.

In terms of mean run time (T_{run}), random search takes shorter times ($4.36E+04$ s) than the other algorithms since it has less internal operations. However, this algorithm converges to the weakest solutions. PSO is the metaheuristic that spent shortest mean running time ($5.38E+04$ s) followed by DE, SA, and GA, respectively.

TABLE V
MEAN EXECUTION TIME (SECONDS) PER INDEPENDENT RUN OF EACH ALGORITHM.

Algorithm	T_{best} (seconds)	T_{run} (seconds)
PSO	3.05E+04	5.38E+04
DE	4.29E+04	7.95E+04
GA	2.04E+04	1.18E+05
SA	5.78E+04	1.04E+05
RAND	3.73E+04	4.36E+04

According to Table V, the analysed algorithms use between $4.36E+04$ and $1.18E+05$ seconds (12.11 and 32.66 hours, respectively) to finish each execution. This effort in the protocol design is completely justified by the subsequent benefits obtained in the global quality of service once the VANET is physically deployed (see Section VI-B).

TABLE VI
RANKINGS IN TERMS OF BEST RETURNED SOLUTION, TIME TO FIND THE OPTIMUM (T_{best}), AND MEAN EXECUTION TIME (T_{run}).

Rank	Global performance	T_{best}	T_{run}
#1	SA	GA	RAND
#2	DE	PSO	PSO
#3	PSO	RAND	DE
#4	GA	DE	SA
#5	RAND	SA	GA

Table VI summarises three rankings of the compared algorithms in terms of: the global performance solving the OLSR optimisation problem, the mean time in which the best solution was found (T_{best}), and the mean run time (T_{run}). Thus, the best algorithm if there is not any time restriction is SA, since it is the one ranked with the best global performance. However, PSO offers the best trade-off between the time requirements and the quality of the returned solution.

B. Optimised versus Human Expert Configurations

In this section, we focus our analysis to the solution domain point of view. Then we compare the resulted OLSR configurations in terms of selected QoS indicators (PDR , NRL , and $E2ED$). To start with, we can see in Table VII the OLSR parameter settings considered for comparison in this analysis. In this table, columns 2 to 4 contain three human expert configurations (#1, #2, and #3) proposed in Gómez et al. [17]; columns 5 and 6 contain the OLSR configurations of the standard RFC 3626, and the one obtained by the random search algorithm, respectively; columns 7 to 10 show the best OLSR configurations obtained by each one of the four metaheuristic algorithms studied in this work: PSO, DE, GA, and SA.

TABLE VII

OLSR PARAMETER VALUES IN CONFIGURATIONS OF THE STATE OF THE ART (GÓMEZ ET AL.), THE STANDARD RFC 3626, AND THE BEST SOLUTIONS IN OPTIMISATION ALGORITHMS.

Parameter	Gómez et al. [17]			OLSR RFC	RAND	Optimal Configurations			
	#1	#2	#3			DE	PSO	GA	SA
HELLO_INTERVAL	0.50 s	1.0 s	4.0 s	2.0 s	3.730204 s	8.47749 s	8.90893 s	8.56877 s	9.00492 s
REFRESH_INTERVAL	0.50 s	1.0 s	4.0 s	2.0 s	6.188079 s	1.08588 s	9.66322 s	15.8294 s	4.92475 s
TC_INTERVAL	1.25 s	2.5 s	10.0 s	5.0 s	5.188182 s	7.24568 s	7.19176 s	5.28564 s	6.75348 s
WILLINGNESS	3	3	3	3	4	0	1	1	0
NEIGHB_HOLD_TIME	1.50 s	3.0 s	12.0 s	6.0 s	5.400073 s	16.9243 s	67.2384 s	83.7708 s	80.3338 s
TOP_HOLD_TIME	3.75 s	7.5 s	20.0 s	15.0 s	40.163638 s	99.0613 s	72.6929 s	67.6192 s	80.9653 s
MID_HOLD_TIME	3.75 s	7.5 s	20.0 s	15.0 s	34.475654 s	6.71314 s	91.3026 s	37.105 s	2.91286 s
DUP_HOLD_TIME	30.0 s	30.0 s	30.0 s	30.0 s	31.515425 s	71.9379 s	21.5715 s	16.268 s	16.7045 s

TABLE VIII

COMPARISONS OF CONSIDERED OLSR CONFIGURATIONS IN TERMS OF THREE QoS INDICATORS.

Metric	Gómez et al. [17]			OLSR RFC	RAND	Optimal Configurations			
	#1	#2	#3			DE	PSO	GA	SA
<i>PDR</i>	71.43%	87.50%	93.34%	91.67%	94.12%	100.00%	100.00%	100.00%	100.00%
<i>NRL</i>	1608.90 kbps	568.50 kbps	273.79 kbps	174.64 kbps	138.75 kbps	54.33 kbps	55.66 kbps	262.43 kbps	96.86 kbps
<i>E2ED</i>	5.41 ms	5.03 ms	7.19 ms	6.29 ms	6.57 ms	15.60 ms	11.31 ms	19.17 ms	4.73 ms

The results of simulating our VANET scenario instance of Málaga city with these OLSR configurations are presented in Table VIII and (graphically) in Fig. 4. Note that the figure is in logarithmic scale in order to ease its representation. Our observations are those:

- Examining the PDR indicator, we can effectively check that the four metaheuristic algorithms obtained a 100% in contrast with the random search algorithm that achieved a 94.12% and the remaining configurations that obtained PDRs between 71.43% and 93.34%. This is an important issue, since a low packet delivery ratio directly implies a higher packet loss.

- Concerning the NRL, similar results can be observed. That is, almost all optimised OLSR configurations showed better routing loads than the other proposals. Only GA (the worst ranked metaheuristic) obtained a NRL (262.43 kbps) worse than the two ones obtained by the standard configuration and RAND (174.64 kbps and 138.75 kbps, respectively), although better than the three human expert configurations (#1 with 1608.90 kbps, #2 with 568.50 kbps, and #3 with 174.64 kbps). In general, DE generated the lowest routing load (54.33 kbps) followed by PSO (55.66 kbps). These results contrast with all other configurations since DE and PSO outperformed the rest by one order of magnitude (two in the case of #1). Reducing the routing load is important since this is a way to reduce the possibility of network failures because of congestion [9], which is a problem in VANETs [43].

- Finally, in terms of the E2ED, we can notice that SA obtained the best result (4.73 ms), followed by human experts configurations (Gómez et al.), standard RFC 3626, and RAND. In this case, the remaining metaheuristic algorithms (PSO, DE, and GA) showed a moderate performance. Evidently, the low routing load experimented in these configurations limited the routing management operations, hence making the average E2ED worse than other configurations with high routing load. However, it is remarkable that all optimised OLSR parameter settings analysed here send the packets with a delay shorter than 20 ms, which is the highest allowed latency for co-operative vehicular safety applications [3], the most critical ones.

Fig. 4. QoS comparisons between the different OLSR configurations. In general, all optimised configurations outperform (higher PDR, lower NRL, and lower E2ED) the other proposals.

C. Global QoS Analysis

In this section we analyze the impact of some interesting OLSR parameters in the global performance of a given configuration. Table VII presents the configurations taken into account in this study.

Generally, according to our tests, reducing the *HELLO_INTERVAL* and *TC_INTERVAL* parameters may help to improve the OLSR reactivity to the route changes and the link failures, for this reason the shorter HELLO and TC intervals the lower E2ED (see Gómez, RFC, and RAND OLSR parameter settings in tables VII and VIII). Nevertheless, this causes an increase in protocol load (NRL) being very likely to cause network congestion and packet loss (lower PDR), that is, reducing the number of nodes that can be accurately communicating in the network. In fact, as TC messages are broadcasted to the whole network, the NRL is reduced critically by increasing *TC_INTERVAL* parameter (see DE and PSO OLSR parameter settings in Table VII and Figure 4).

Something similar happens with the *NEIGHB_HOLD_TIME* and the *TOP_HOLD_TIME* timers, because in the metaheuristic optimized OLSR parameter settings they are larger than the other ones. The need of protocol management information update seems to be lower than the proposed in Gómez and OLSR 3626 RFC configurations, since the communications carried out by using the PSO, DE, GA, and SA OLSR routing protocols exchanged correctly all the packets (PDR = 100%) within a time of lower than 20 ms (highest allowed latency).

VII. CONCLUSIONS

In this work we have addressed the optimal parameter tuning of the OLSR routing protocol to be used in vehicular *ad hoc* networks. For this task, we have defined an optimisation strategy based on coupling optimisation algorithms and the *ns-2* network simulator. The used algorithms are four different metaheuristic algorithms (PSO, DE, GA, and SA) selected with the aim of experimenting with different population structures and reproduction mechanisms. In addition, we have compared the optimised OLSR configurations with the standard one in RFC 3626, as well

as with human expert configurations found in the current state of the art. In order to assess the performance of resulted configurations, we have defined a urban VANET instance based on real data of the city downtown of Málaga (Spain) following realistic mobility and data flow models. In the light of the experimental results we can conclude that:

- The performance of automatically optimised OLSR improves significantly the standard configuration of OLSR. Additionally, optimised configurations transmit 100% of the packets, increasing the packet delivery rate regarding the standard configuration by 8.34%.
- The OLSR configurations provided by the experts under-perform the automatic tuned ones using metaheuristics. In average, the PDR obtained by the experts configurations is 15.91% lower and generates up to 1554.57 kbps more load than the optimised ones.
- In terms of the time needed to transmit the data packets (E2ED), all studied OLSR configurations transmit packets within the limits established for this particular kind of networks.
- Globally, SA outperforms the other studied metaheuristic algorithms when solving the OLSR optimisation problem, it is the best ranked by the Friedman test.
- PSO presents the best trade-off between the performance and the execution time requirements.
- Finally, concerning the solution domain, the configuration of OLSR generated by SA offers the best trade-off between the three QoS indicators considered in this work.

The optimisation methodology presented in this work (coupling metaheuristics and a simulation process) offers the possibility of automatically and efficiently customising any protocol for any VANET scenario.

As a matter of further work we are currently extending our experiments with new still larger urban and highway VANET instances. In addition, we are defining new optimised configuration schemes for other communication protocols such as: WAVE, UDP, etc. which should efficiently support actual VANET design. Finally, we are planning new real tests (using vehicles travelling through different kinds of roads) in order to validate our simulations.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

Authors acknowledge funds from the Spanish Ministry MICINN and FEDER under contract TIN2008-06491-C04-01 (M* <http://mstar.lcc.uma.es>) and CICE, Junta de Andalucía, under contract P07-TIC-03044 (DIRICOM <http://diricom.lcc.uma.es>). José García-Nieto is supported by grant BES-2009-018767 from the MICINN

REFERENCES

- [1] H. Hartenstein and K. Laberteaux, *VANET Vehicular applications and inter-networking technologies*, dec 2009.
- [2] CARLINK, "CARLINK European EUREKA-CELTIC Label CP3-005," [online] Available in URL <http://carlink.lcc.uma.es>.

- [3] CAMP, "Vehicle Safety Communications Consortium (2005). Vehicle safety communications project task 3 final report: Identify intelligent vehicle applications enabled by DSRC." CAMP, Washington, DC, Tech. Rep., 2005, [Online]. Available: <http://ntl.bts.gov/lib/29000/29500/29505/CAMP3scr.pdf>.
- [4] X. Xie, F. Wang, K. Li, P. Zhang, and H. Wang, "Improvement of multi-channel MAC protocol for dense VANET with directional antennas," in *Wireless Communications and Networking Conference, 2009. WCNC 2009. IEEE*, 2009, pp. 1–6.
- [5] N. Lu, Y. Ji, F. Liu, and X. Wang, "A dedicated multi-channel MAC protocol design for VANET with adaptive broadcasting," in *Wireless Communications and Networking Conference (WCNC), 2010 IEEE*, 2010, pp. 1–6.
- [6] T. Taleb, E. Sakhaee, A. Jamalipour, K. Hashimoto, N. Kato, and Y. Nemoto, "A stable routing protocol to support ITS services in VANET networks," *Vehicular Technology, IEEE Transactions on*, vol. 56, no. 6, pp. 3337–3347, 2007.
- [7] T. Taleb, M. Ochi, A. Jamalipour, N. Kato, and Y. Nemoto, "An efficient vehicle-heading based routing protocol for VANET networks," in *Wireless Communications and Networking Conference, 2006. WCNC 2006. IEEE*, vol. 4, 2006, pp. 2199–2204.
- [8] C. L. Ramírez, S. C. Umaña, and M. F. Veiga, "QoS and multipath routing in vehicular network," in *Proceedings of the 2007 Euro American conference on Telematics and information systems*, ser. EATIS '07. New York, NY, USA: ACM, 2007, pp. 6:1–6:7.
- [9] W. Zhang, A. Festag, R. Baldessari, and L. Le, "Congestion control for safety messages in VANETs: Concepts and framework," in *ITS Telecommunications, 2008. ITST 2008. 8th International Conference on*, 2008, pp. 199–203.
- [10] T. Clausen and P. Jacquet, "Optimized Link State Routing Protocol (OLSR)," IETF RFC 3626, [online] Available in URL <http://www.ietf.org/rfc/rfc3626.txt>, United States, 2003.
- [11] T. Chen, O. Mehani, and R. Boreli, "Trusted routing for VANET," in *ITST 2009, 9th International Conference on Intelligent Transport Systems Telecommunications*, M. Berbineau, M. Itami, and G. Wen, Eds. Piscataway, NJ, USA: IEEE Computer Society, October 2009, pp. 647–652.
- [12] J. Haerri, C. Bonnet, and F. Filali, "Analysis of vehicular mobility patterns on routing protocols," Institut Eurecom, France, Tech. Rep. EURECOM+2241, 08 2006.
- [13] A. Laouiti, P. Mühlenthaler, F. Sayah, and Y. Toor, "Quantitative evaluation of the cost of routing protocol OLSR in a Vehicle Ad Hoc Network (VANET)," in *VTC Spring. IEEE*, 2008, pp. 2986–2990.
- [14] F. Rango, J. Cano, M. Fotino, C. Calafate, P. Manzoni, and S. Marano, "OLSR vs DSR: A comparative analysis of proactive and reactive mechanisms from an energetic point of view in wireless ad hoc networks," *Computer Communications*, vol. 31, no. 16, pp. 3843–3854, October 2008.
- [15] J. Santa, M. Tsukada, T. Ernst, O. Mehani, and A. F. Gómez-Skarmeta, "Assessment of VANET multi-hop routing over an experimental platform," *Int. J. Internet Protoc. Technol.*, vol. 4, no. 3, pp. 158–172, 2009.
- [16] Y. Huang, S. Bhatti, and D. Parker, "Tuning OLSR," in *Proceedings of the IEEE 17th International Symposium on Personal, Indoor and Mobile Radio Communications, PIMRC, Helsinki, Finland*, 2006, pp. 1–5.
- [17] C. Gómez, D. García, and J. Paradells, "Improving performance of a real ad hoc network by tuning OLSR parameters," in *ISCC '05: Proceedings of the 10th IEEE Symposium on Computers and Communications*. Washington, DC, USA: IEEE Computer Society, 2005, pp. 16–21.
- [18] C. Blum and A. Roli, "Metaheuristics in combinatorial optimization: Overview and conceptual comparison," *ACM Computing Surveys*, vol. 35, no. 3, pp. 268–308, 2003.
- [19] A. Fink and S. Voss, "Generic metaheuristics application to industrial engineering problems," *Computers and Industrial Engineering*, vol. 37, no. 1-2, pp. 281–284, 1999, proceedings of the 24th international conference on computers and industrial engineering.
- [20] K. Parsopoulos and F. Vrahatis, "Unified particle swarm optimization for solving constrained engineering optimization problems," in *Advances in Natural Computation*. Springer, 2005, pp. 582–591.

- [21] Y. Xu and R. Qu, "A hybrid scatter search meta-heuristic for delay-constrained multicast routing problems," *Applied Intelligence*, pp. 1–13, October 2010.
- [22] E. Alba, J. García-Nieto, J. Taheri, and A. Zomaya, "New research in nature inspired algorithms for mobility management in GSM networks," in *LNCS of the Fifth European Workshop on the Application of Nature-inspired Techniques to Telecommunication Networks and other Connected Systems, EvoWorkshops08*. Napoli Italy: Springer-Verlag, 2008, pp. 1–10.
- [23] E. A. et al., "A Cellular MOGA for Optimal Broadcasting Strategy in Metropolitan MANETs," *Computer Communications*, vol. 30, no. 4, pp. 685 – 697, 2007.
- [24] B. Dorransoro, G. Danoy, P. Bouvry, and E. Alba, "Evaluation of different optimization techniques in the design of ad hoc injection networks," in *Workshop on Optimization Issues in Grid and Parallel Computing Environments, part of the HPCS*, Nicossia, Cyprus, 2008, pp. 290–296.
- [25] H. Cheng and S. Yang, "Genetic algorithms with immigrant schemes for dynamic multicast problems in mobile ad hoc networks," *Eng. Appl. Artif. Intell.*, vol. 23, pp. 806–819, August 2010.
- [26] H. Shokrani and S. Jabbehdari, "A novel ant-based QoS routing for mobile ad hoc networks," in *ICUFN'09: Proceedings of the first international conference on Ubiquitous and future networks*. Piscataway, NJ, USA: IEEE Press, 2009, pp. 79–82.
- [27] C. Huang, Y. Chuang, and K. Hu, "Using particle swarm optimization for QoS in ad-hoc multicast," *Eng. Appl. Artif. Intell.*, vol. 22, pp. 1188–1193, December 2009.
- [28] J. García-Nieto, J. Toutouh, and E. Alba, "Automatic tuning of communication protocols for vehicular ad hoc networks using metaheuristics," *Engineering Applications of Artificial Intelligence*, vol. 23, no. 5, pp. 795–805, 2010.
- [29] J. Kennedy and R. Eberhart, "Particle Swarm Optimization," *IEEE International Conference on Neural Networks*, vol. 4, pp. 1942–1948, Nov 1995.
- [30] K. V. Price, R. Storn, and J. Lampinen, *Differential Evolution: A practical Approach to Global Optimization*. London, UK: Springer-Verlag, 2005.
- [31] D. E. Goldberg, *Genetic Algorithms in Search Optimization and Machine Learning*. Addison-Wesley, 1989.
- [32] S. Kirkpatrick, C. D. Gelatt, and M. P. Vecchi, "Optimization by Simulated Annealing," *Science*, vol. 220, no. 4598, pp. 671–680, 1983.
- [33] "The Network Simulator Project - Ns-2," [online] <http://www.isi.edu/nsnam/ns/>.
- [34] D. Nguyen and P. Minet, "Analysis of MPR selection in the OLSR protocol," *Advanced Information Networking and Applications Workshops, International Conference on*, vol. 2, pp. 887–892, 2007.
- [35] V. Naumov, R. Baumann, and T. Gross, "An evaluation of inter-vehicle ad hoc networks based on realistic vehicular traces," in *Proceedings of the 7th ACM MobiHoc*. New York, NY, USA: ACM, 2006, pp. 108–119.
- [36] Y. Nourani and B. Andresen, "A comparison of simulated annealing cooling strategies," *Journal of Physics A: Mathematical and General*, pp. 8373–8385, 1998.
- [37] E. Alba, S. Luna, and J. Toutouh, "Accuracy and efficiency in simulating VANETs." in *MCO*, ser. Communications in Computer and Information Science, L. T. H. An, P. Bouvry, and T. P. Dinh, Eds., vol. 14. Springer, 2008, pp. 568–578.
- [38] J. Härrri, F. Filali, and C. Bonnet, "Mobility Models for Vehicular Ad Hoc Networks: A Survey and Taxonomy," no. Research Report RR-06-168, March 2007.
- [39] D. Krajzewicz, M. Bonert, and P. Wagner, "The open source traffic simulation package SUMO," in *RoboCup'06*, Bremen, Germany, 2006, pp. 1–10.
- [40] E. Alba, G. Luque, J. García-Nieto, G. Ordonez, and G. Leguizamón, "MALLBA: A software library to design efficient optimisation algorithms," *Int. Journal of Innovative Computing and Applications (IJICA)*, vol. 1, no. 1, pp. 74–85, 2007.
- [41] "UM-OLSR implementation (University of Murcia)," [online] Available in URL <http://masimum.dif.um.es/?Software:UM-OLSR>.

- [42] D. J. Sheskin, *Handbook of Parametric and Nonparametric Statistical Procedures*. Chapman & Hall/CRC, 2007.
- [43] L. Wischhof and H. Rohling, "Congestion control in vehicular ad hoc networks," in *Vehicular Electronics and Safety, 2005. IEEE International Conference on*, 2005, pp. 58 – 63.
- [44] J. Toutouh and E. Alba, "Performance analysis of optimized VANET protocols in real world tests," in *submitted to Wireless Communications and Mobile Computing 2011 (IWCMC 2011)*, Istanbul, Turkey, 2011.
- [45] E. Alba, J. Toutouh, and S. Luna, "D1.3.5-Comparison between simulations and real tests (CARLINK-UMA scenario)," University of Malaga, Spain, Tech. Rep., 2007. [Online]. Available: <http://carlink.lcc.uma.es>